

Minimum Standard Operating Protocols on Managing or Supporting Joint/Interagency Complaints and Feedback Mechanism

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1.) Background

There are always advantages or benefits of maximizing any form of joint/interagency approach when it comes to a responsive complaints and feedback mechanism (CFM) that will effectively communicate to the at-risk communities and inclusively engage with the affected people.

More than just practicalities, simplifying bureaucracies or agreements, improving relationships or partnerships, and enhancing each other's platform or channels, a joint/interagency CFM always provide opportunities to further improve and recalibrate capacities and resources as necessary, and ensure it stay relevant, of added-value, and still fit for purpose.

The joint/interagency¹ CFM highly supports the overarching commitment and framework on the accountability to affected people (AAP) to ensure information is accessible and inclusive, feedback and complaints are properly addressed or responded, and meaningful participation is consistently supported.

As part of the call-for-action to operationalize a joint/interagency CFM, this minimum operations protocol is developed to support a more localized and contextualized implementations of identified and prioritized two-way channels by the responding agencies to engage people and community in the Occupied Palestine Territory (OPT).

Basically, the minimum operations protocol aims to simplify how the mechanism works to consistently push or engage the people or agencies that will be involved in managing or supporting it, identify avenues to improve or recalibrate the system to be more functional, and systemically ensure that feedback are not only addressed or referred to successfully, but it contributes to improving the overall response actions.

To enhance those identified channels, a common framework, guidance, tools, indicators, support platforms, and timeline must be appropriately applied and key results of utilizing those, must be shared or referred, and in a likely circumstances, contribute to the shared accountability. More than just a process-oriented undertaking, it ensures that the system supporting the CF channels are clear to all responding or implementing agencies, including partners and third-party operators or consultants.

Having a joint/interagency CFM is also an attempt of the entire humanitarian community to regain the overall trust of the people it serves in OPT. The minimum operations protocol supporting the CF channels is all about respecting, listening, and responding or addressing concerns and issues affecting people while also empowering and supporting their contexts, abilities or capacities, and resources.

With the oversight from the Steering Committee², the joint/interagency CFM will build on the technical and operational capacities of the Accountability to Affected People (AAP) Working Group, Protection

¹ For the purpose of this protocol, a joint/interagency approach instead of a more advanced collective approach will be used. Here, we are focusing here on three or more agencies working or collaborating. Collective is the highest level or scale when it comes to commitment, capacities, and resources to support overall CFM management. Utilizing joint/interagency is the entry point to eventually reach collective process in the long run. The goal is to achieve and sustain, as needed and required, a unified system that is co-managed by various organizations. The process-oriented approach basically supports receiving and making sense of the feedback from the communities within the humanitarian response cycle, including joint analysis and aggregation of feedback for strategic decision-making; and eventually closing the loop and recalibrate response actions.

² Focal points from AAP Working Group and PSEA Network supporting the Gaza Response. Currently, these include UN agencies such as UNICEF, UNOCHA, UNWFP, UNWOMEN, and UNWRA.

against Sexual Exploitation and Abuse (PSEA) Network, and other agencies or partners implementing or supporting impactful community engagement and accountability endeavors.

2.) Objectives

To simplify the processes and ensure the mechanism is practical, contextual, and enabling as possible, the minimum operations protocol aims to:

- Ensure that questions, suggestions, comments, concerns, feedback, and complaints shared by community members³ are responded or referred to in a timely, systematic, and appropriate manner using the preferred and available two-way channels.
- Ensure there is a reliable, accessible, safe, and functional referral process⁴ supporting the CFM for issues or assistance that requires additional support or ensure that they are directly linked to other agency/organization's capacities and resources.
- Ensure that all preferred or available two-way channels have a safe, trusted, and confidential mechanism⁵ to be used in dealing with highly sensitive and serious breaches on accountability such as sexual abuse and exploitation (SEA), security and safety threats, fraud, harassment and maltreatment, child protection and safeguarding concerns, corruption and other abuses or misuses of authority, misconduct and other ethical violations, discriminations and bullying, and other life-threatening issues that may undermine the response actions.
- Ensure that the joint or interagency CFM is sensitive and responsive enough to community voices when it comes to improving and recalibrating, as necessary, the overall humanitarian response programming⁶, and in the process, minimizing lip service engagement⁷.
- Ensure that community voices go beyond the dashboards and other forms of visibility that may be considered as offensive, disrespectful, and harmful by the community --- as much as possible their voices should influence or should serve as the basis to reassess humanitarian response plan/overview (HRP/HNO), situational reports, monitoring/evaluation documents, and any type of after action review.

3.) Common interagency mechanism

Each agency is expected to apply specific mechanism to effectively resolve or address feedback and complaints depending on its identified platforms and how its partners manage to use it. Those involved in the management of CFM are accustomed to the general concept of closing the feedback loop:

Feedback Given, Acknowledgement, Analysis, Action Taken (or not) and Response to Community.

Unpacking all these requires activities and processes to ensure each step is closely followed and that the complete process is not hampered in a particular phase that may result to not closing the cycle.

³ Elder people, women, men, persons with disabilities, ethnic/religious/minorities, LGBTIQ (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Intersex or Questioning), children, girls, boys, less educated, less vocal/less visible, and those living in isolated or remote areas.

⁴ All responding agencies with established CFM are expected to adapt its own referral system and collaborate with other organizations as deem necessary.

⁵ Maximizing the existing referral system by the PSEA Network.

⁶ Contributing to the overall commitment on AAP framework and grounded participation revolution.

⁷ Convenient solution of humanitarian agencies in dealing with the recurring complain across humanitarian responses as opposed to solutions that improve or disrupt unresponsive system.

For a common approach, this protocol will adopt the 7Rs for responsive and functional system⁸. While each platform or channel used may require different process to collect information and reply to feedback, the principle behind the 7Rs may still apply on it and does not limit or affect the overall minimum process.

a.) Receiving

The process of capturing feedback, complaints, suggestions, and other serious breaches on accountability.

b.) Recording

The process of documenting, classifying, categorizing, and making sense of the information received.

c.) Reviewing

The process of revalidating, verifying, and identifying the likely actions or support needed to address the feedback, complaints, and other serious breaches on accountability.

d.) Referring

The process of seeking additional support and other technical capacities or resources needed to address feedback, sensitive complaints, and other serious breaches of accountability or those that need immediate, specific, special and urgent actions beyond the capacity of one or two responding agencies.

e.) Responding

The likely action or attempt to address feedback, complaints/other serious breaches on accountability and close the process in the soonest appropriate time possible. This can be done jointly or collectively.

f.) Recalibrating⁹

The process of changing, disrupting, and transforming the system to be more responsive and functional to the needs of the affected people and at-risk communities based on documented results or outcome. This may include improving or changing the approach to providing aid or ensuring that the overall support is still appropriate and fit for purpose.

g.) Reporting back to the communities

The last and the most important process of the system. This is to ensure overall transparency as well as trust and preference of the people on the channels/mechanisms they have used or maximized to provide feedback are sustained, supported, and enhanced.

⁸ Each agency has their own system and mechanism in place that can be utilized. But for the purpose of a more common understanding and simplified adoption of the system, the 7Rs are underscored in this protocol.

⁹ Most overlooked process and one of the key reasons why it's needed in most humanitarian actions is that there is a low trust with the CF channels.

4.) Data management and responsibility

Any joint/interagency initiative that deals with people's data requires appropriate compliance to legal framework and safety/security measures on data management.

In line with the Inter-Agency Steering Committee's (IASC) operational guidance on data responsibility in humanitarian action¹⁰, it is recommended that agencies that will be managing and supporting joint/interagency CFM strictly follow and comply with the additional minimum agreements, standards, and commitments stipulated.

Each agency or organization has its own data management and each organization is expected to apply or contextualize those if they enter into any form of partnership with one or more organizations. The same applies when the organization works or enters into an agreement or partnership with other partners or third-party service providers (*like hotline/helpline, radio, and social media operators or consultants*). The “do no harm” principle is basically the overarching impetus for this to ensure there is a common ground towards data sharing and protection.

As all responding agencies¹¹ have their own CF channels and expected to support the joint/interagency CFM protocol, they need to be aware of and adopt, as needed and required, the following¹²:

- Data responsibility diagnostic
- Data management registry
- Data impact assessment
- Designing for data responsibility
- Information sharing protocol
- Data sharing agreement
- Data incident agreement

This protocol will also apply and contextualize core principles¹³ that would enhance its day-to-day data monitoring, reporting, and sharing. Adapting the principles is an effort to put some balance and check on the way various organizations and partners strictly adhere to the safe, ethical, and effective approach to receiving data and the way it is being used appropriately in the process.

a.) Accountability – being accountable to people and community we serve is always about the transparency from the get-go of what the interagency CFM is all about, who are the people or agency that will be involved, do they have the necessary capacities and resources when it comes to collecting or receiving data and what corresponding processes does it entail in order to address, respond, and refer to successfully those data.

b.) Confidentiality – any joint/interagency CFM must not only prioritize the inclusive and accessible process of receiving and addressing the feedback or complaints, but must also

¹⁰ <https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/operational-response/iasc-operational-guidance-data-responsibility-humanitarian-action>

¹¹ There are agencies who have already entered a partnership and collaboration that requires them to sign a particular agreement on data management and responsibility.

¹² Corresponding templates for each agreement/commitment can also be downloaded via this link:

<https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/sites/default/files/migrated/2023-04/IASC%20Operational%20Guidance%20on%20Data%20Responsibility%20in%20Humanitarian%20Action%2C%202023.pdf>

¹³ All agencies with corresponding CFM have their own core principles or components adapted when it comes to overall data management. The list above provides common understanding and approach to make sense of the process of sharing, reporting, etc.

warrant a dedicated safe and secure system to keep sensitive data, provide access restrictions, and employ legal support in case of breach in protocol.

- c.) **Coordination and collaboration** –the success of any joint/interagency initiatives relies heavily on how various agencies work together efficiently to get hold of the system or mechanism dealing with diverse issues and unprecedented challenges.
- d.) **Data Security** – aside from confidentiality, sensitive data require secure and safe management measures. Secured data means a solid prevention and mitigation system is in place to address issues related to security and safety breaches, accidental or intentional disclosure of data, damages or loss, accidental or unauthorized or inappropriate internal access or manipulation of information resulting to use and misuse, and other security risks related to data management, which continue to undermine the potential capacity of any channels or platforms that collect and manage big data.
- e.) **Purpose, Necessity, and Proportionality** – the design for the joint/interagency CFM is part of the call-for-action to maximize available resources to effectively communicate and engage with the affected people. The identified solutions¹⁴ cater specifically to the challenges that require collective response actions and consistent to the available or identified two-way channels with dedicated services and capacities from the humanitarian agencies.
- f.) **Fairness and Legitimacy** – the basis to complement, augment, and supplement preferred or trusted two-way channels of the affected people is consistent with the overarching commitment to abide with the humanitarian principles on neutrality and impartiality and ensure it is of added-value to what the community wanted and needed. Agencies that will manage and support interagency CFM will abide with any in-country legal, legitimate, and applicable laws to ensure the safety, security, and overall interest of the community.
- g.) **Human Rights-Based, People Centered, and Inclusive-Focused Approaches** – more than anything else, fundamental data specific and any other access rights of the people must always be upheld, protected, and safeguarded. Data responsibility management cannot function without such from the get-go. Anchored on the “no one should be left behind” principle, data management requires consistent and reliable standards and mechanisms to ensure the most marginalized, vulnerable, less vocal, less visible, less educated, and less engaged will be given priority and opportunity to provide data and access data as they see fit and necessary.
- h.) **Personal Data Protection** - aside from confidentiality and access security, it is imperative that any CFM has a system that protects privacy and personal data. Agencies entering into any form of partnerships or collaborations with third party agency should always be cautious about the importance of people’s right to be informed. Individual’s consent is crucial when it comes to meaningful engagement (sharing and accessing data) and each is entitled to be engaged in an appropriate, safe, and confidential manner.
- i.) **Quality** - For this protocol, it is always important to receive, record, and review sex, age, disability or diversity disaggregated data (SADD++) to capture inclusively gaps, challenges, and issues affecting the community. The primary reason why there is a call-to-action for a joint/interagency CFM is to ensure the humanitarian community has the right and quality data to inform its decision and improve the response actions.

¹⁴ Including those activities or projects not cover or supported by the Central Emergency Response Fund (CERF).

- j.) **Transparency** - as part supporting the reporting back to the communities, the joint/interagency CFM will endeavor to scale-up the raising of awareness on the accessibility and inclusivity of the two-way channels including the step-by-step sharing of data, how it is being managed or processed, and what can be expected when it comes to the overall support mechanism.

5.) Trusted and preferred two-way channels

This joint/interagency protocol focuses on applying the closing the loop system on the minimum available¹⁵ and preferred channels¹⁶. The identified channels are complementary to support in the best way possible the face-to-face dialogue and to find other available avenues that can affirm more interpersonal level engagement with the community members in OPT.

Two-way channels such as hotline/helpline, humanitarian radio programming, social media engagement and listening, and joint field missions (*assessment, community consultations, and monitoring*) are considered hybrid or combined solutions¹⁷ that can meaningfully engage the people in OPT.

Understanding the classification, characteristics, and contexts of each two-way channel is important considering all of those need to be linked up and warrant the expertise of concerned agencies to essentially guarantee that those channels are diverse, inclusive, and responsive enough to regain trust issues, address access and safety restrictions, and amend response actions for necessary course correction.

As part of supporting the joint/interagency CFM, this protocol welcomes as many responding agencies as possible to collaborate and enter into any form of partnership or agreement with other agencies¹⁸ (*including third party service providers and operators*) using two or more channels. There are benefits to have many agencies jointly using common service platforms as these underscored the opportunity to improve the use of each channel, expand the reach of engaging at-risk communities and displaced people, and strengthen the overarching shared accountability to the community.

The call-to-action supporting the interagency CFM using various channels is basically to underscore the following:

- To have one unified humanitarian hotline/helpline supported by common service directory platform¹⁹, simplified referral process, and additional customer relations management software/applications to manage cases²⁰.
- To maximize humanitarian radio programming with common FAQs and referral process to support listening group and ensure it can be integrated with the use of hotline/helpline.

¹⁵ As provided by the responding agencies and based on its previous engagement in an armed-conflict, prolonged displacement, and evolving humanitarian crisis.

¹⁶ Pertains to channels that people preferred for two-way dialogue and at the minimum, can be supported by the responding agencies.

¹⁷ Use of analog (may not require technology) and digital (relies heavily on technology and software solution) channels. The use of radio and helpline/hotline can be maximized as analog and digital, while social media is technology/platform based, and field missions are dependent on face-to-face dialogue.

¹⁸ For now, both WFP and UNICEF are using same hotline/helpline under joint/interagency agreement.

¹⁹ Common AAP service directory managed by UNOCHA

²⁰ To be developed and commissioned by UN Women

- To maximize social media listening engagement²¹ with common listening tools to monitor rumors, misinformation, and disinformation that could undermine the overall humanitarian response actions.
- To conduct joint/interagency field mission using common service tools on assessment, community consultations, and monitoring through community assembly/meetings, focus group, consultation, key informant dialogue, and information session caravan.

In terms of sharing information, addressing jointly issues and concerns, and facilitating referral process, the following will play critical roles²² in each of the identified two-way channel²³:

- **Team lead/coordinator per channel:** expected to share information (*including trends and analyzed reports*) to agencies supporting the interagency CFM in various meetings (*working group in some instances with the HCT and ICCG*).
- **Operations manager per channel:** this could be second focal point to the team lead/coordinator in sharing information but this role is expected to provide more technical contributions in terms of the day-to-day operations and how to improve it by engaging various agencies especially on those considered as unresolved cases, complaints, and issues.
- **Referral focal point per channel:** expected to provide update on issues contributing or not to the success of the overall referral process.
- **Receiving/responding focal point per channel:** expected to provide update how cases or issues have been resolved or not given the timeline, indicators, and capacities or resources.

²¹ Both radio programming and social media engagement will be commissioned by UNOCHA and UNWOMEN.

²² The roles and functions may vary per agency co-managing a particular channel, but it is important to have focal point on sharing the information and referral process.

²³ This pertains to helpline/hotline, humanitarian radio programming, and social media engagement.

<u>Platforms/ Channels</u>	<u>Contexts</u>	<u>Managing capacities, resources, limitations, and other operational considerations</u>	<u>Avenues for collective, coordinated, interagency, and joint approach</u>
<p>Hotline/Helpline²⁴</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It may not be as the most preferred or trusted channel by the affected people, but at this point, this is one of the most useful available channels as face-to-face dialogue on a regular basis is almost impossible for humanitarian staff. - Across OPT, the helpline/hotline can reach wide range of people or community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Setting up a helpline/hotline requires budget and resources even for short or temporary engagement. Like other emergencies, this requires dedicated staff management, strict protocols, and careful integration of other channels considering the demand for wide coverage and outreach. - Although can be augmented by other channels, even the use of helpline/hotline can exclude the most vulnerable members of the community such as persons with disabilities, people without phones or those in an area with poor mobile coverage, and those considered as less educated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WFP/UNICEF are currently doing a joint undertaking on the use of hotline. There is an existing protocol between WFP and UNICEF. - One way to expand the hotline is to have an interagency protocol on referral and enter any form of collaborations on shared accountability. - Another is to integrate additional CRM/software solution that would complement existing case management system. This could support in following up cases and closing the loop.
<p>Radio²⁵</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most used and available channel in a community (both at the personal or household level) as source of information. - Among the channels, if radio is properly maximized, it has the capacity to reach wider reach and audiences across OPT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One key issue is the access people without radio. But this can be resolved if within the community someone has access to radio. - This may not be costly but requires strict guidance/protocol for sensitization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working with radio operators and available humanitarian radio programmers to adopt/integrate common service tools can maximize the reach and engagement to the affected people. - Radio operators and humanitarian radio programmers can support continuous raising awareness campaign to regain the trust of the people to the humanitarian

²⁴To be complemented with the use of SMS, Interactive Voice Response, Chatbot, and other Digital Platforms as possible.

²⁵Supporting both traditional/mainstream media and other humanitarian radio operators or programmers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The use of radio is also a great entry point to engage people on a two-way dialogue and it has the component to integrate other channels (like SMS, calls, and use of listening groups) for meaningful participation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Listening group could support vulnerable groups (persons with disabilities, less educated, and those with limited access to radio). 	<p>system and champion the interagency collaborations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some humanitarian agencies are distributing radios as a lifesaving aid. This could boost the level of engagement of people or community through listening groups.
<p>Focus group²⁶, listening group²⁷, and other forms of interpersonal dialogue with the community²⁸</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no substitute with a direct dialogue with the people as it offers great opportunity to close the loop in a more meaningful process. - Investing on this or finding avenues to support this can be equivalent to providing meaningful outreach and capacity building purposes as well. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This will require sufficient, careful planning considering the evolving situations. - The process can be tedious depending on the interpersonal skill sets of the people facilitating the two-way dialogue. - This requires combining the FGD and Listening Groups considering the limited number of people that will be engaged in the process. Substantial and qualitative as it may be, but this can be an issue when it comes to the representation of the people. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working with field level partners could still be an option considering the limited access and security concerns. Provision of capacity building may take some time and resources but that could be entry point to explore other innovative approaches. - Joint or collective field mission could provide the likely boost in the overall trust to humanitarian agencies.

²⁶ In any focus group, it is imperative to consult women, children, persons with disabilities, elderlies, sickly, any identified minorities, geographically isolated, and those considered as the less visible members of the community.

²⁷ Although usually formed as part of supporting humanitarian radio programming, listening group can also be supported as likely alternative to further complement focus group. This can be formed by mixing different people (gender, status, etc.) and can be useful as it also gives you the pulse of the community, and can be maximized to inform and improve all levels of program decision making. Listening group cultivate a sense of community ownership, engagement, and participation, which is not only critical to efficient and effective program delivery but also promotes a sense of resilience in the midst of a crisis.

²⁸ As much as possible be mindful of any existing or established community structure as they are considered good entry points to communicate and engage with the affected people or at-risk communities.

<p>Social media²⁹ and other digital messaging applications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - So far, the most versatile of all channels in terms of components, how people can maximize it, has the wider reach or scope, can be integrated to other channels, and a good platform for sharing and engaging larger audience in one go. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The downside of this is that it is difficult to control, can be easily “weaponized” for rumors, misinformation, disinformation, and bad information, and requires some resources or capacities to manage data collection. - At this point, digital access and digital divide are key issues for excluding people without smartphones/mobile data/Wi-Fi. - This could also exclude or alienate vulnerable people and those not using social/digital media at all. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hiring of third-party consultant to work closely with responding agencies requires strict guidance and protocol considering this could undermine the ongoing humanitarian response. - It is crucial that the third-party consultant has the required capacity to customized access to a database that allows concerned agencies to track and monitor social sentiments - Ensure that software to be used are far capable of Big Data analysis and has a stable and viable data monitor and management system to collect, store and analyze data automatically. - Ensure that all identified monitoring, listening, and tracking tools are disability and gender inclusive. This is again to put some context of ensuring we are not excluding everyone (as always the case even with the use of hotline, etc.)
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²⁹Not limited to the popular applications such as WhatsApp, Telegram, and Viber but also other emerging applications that are trusted or preferred by the affected people and at-risk communities.

6.) Minimum roles and responsibilities

The Steering Committee on joint/interagency CFM will provide guidance on how to deal with any sensitive complaints escalated or reported by the designated coordinators, operation managers and referral support staff of each channel. Its primary role is to ensure agencies or organizations consistently use the minimum referral management process that systematically record, monitor, and make follow-up on referrals.

To provide strategic and operational oversight on how these two-way channels can be maximized in a more collaborative manner, focal points from UNOCHA, UNICEF, UNWOMEN, WFP, UNWRA, and other agencies or partners (*members of the AAP Working Group, PSEA Network, and others*) will be the core members that will lead the Steering Committee. The focal points pertain to AAP and PSEA advisors or specialists, two-way channels specific lead, and other designated staff with leadership and technical know-how to support the CFM.

For each communication channel there should be corresponding dedicated roles that will manage or support the systematic and responsive process when it comes to receiving information and addressing those as part of closing the loop.

The identified roles below from each channel are the usual staff or people that manage, and support CF channels based on the previous humanitarian responses. Some of the roles may overlap and, in most instances, one staff performs two or more roles simultaneously. For this protocol, the minimum roles will serve as the common reference, and this may be expanded or limited depending on the institutional arrangements and prior commitments managing a joint/interagency CFM.

The referring and the responding/receiving focal point can be assigned or delegated to staff directly involved in the recording and reviewing of the data collected or received. It is expected that agencies managing or supporting two or more channels will have dedicated staff for each channel.

1.) Helpline/Hotline

Roles	Expected Responsibilities/Functions
Joint Feedback Mechanism Team Lead/Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strategically oversees the organizational structure, functions, and duties of members, providing relevant feedback and other useful data.
Joint Feedback Mechanism Operations Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manages the joint feedback mechanism daily, overseeing and checking that complaints and feedback are forwarded to relevant focal points within the agreed response timeframe, and that necessary follow-ups are made accordingly. ○ Checks that sensitive issues received are immediately and properly directed

	to relevant focal points, making sure that these are handled with strict confidentiality.
Joint Helpline/Hotline Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provides immediate response to inquiries, concerns and complaints received through the joint helpline ○ Consults technical colleagues for inputs regarding concerns aligned to their expertise and liaises with internal staff and external partners to address operational issues and concerns of the joint feedback mechanism.
Community Representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provide immediate response to complaints and feedback onsite, and if needed, record them and upload to database and refer to designated focal points for proper response and handling. ○ Relay feedback directly from at-risk communities and affected people to the corresponding field staff.

2.) Humanitarian Radio Programming

Roles	Expected functions and responsibilities
Project Manager/Operation Head	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Forges partnerships and works closely with respective humanitarian agencies to provide operational needs of the team. ○ In collaboration with the team and partners, drafts operational policies and ensures these are properly carried out. ○ Works closely with partners to create initiatives that would address pressing issues and concerns affecting the community.
Programming Operator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In charge of purchase and maintenance of equipment. ○ Monitors signals and broadcast quality.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintains readiness of studio for programming, recording or remote broadcast. ○ Trains and assists staff and volunteers in operating broadcast equipment. ○ Keeps oneself abreast of the latest technologies that may be utilized to improve current broadcast operations
In-house capacity building officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provides basic reporting training to community correspondents. ○ Provides guidance and mentorship to correspondents particularly on how to report conflict and sensitive humanitarian issues and stories ○ Regularly reviews on-air quality and programming contents
Programming Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provides support in developing the broadcasting guidelines and policies. ○ Edits and checks content for clarity, correctness, and conformity to set guidelines before broadcast. ○ Observes trends, issues, and developments that may affect programming. ○ Maintains a library of recordings, audio files and other resources
Community Correspondents/Reporters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conducts interviews, research information, collect data, and prepare reports on assigned issues and stories. ○ Continuously engages in activities to improve journalism and broadcasting skills and learn new technologies. ○ As the face of the station, conducts functions with utmost professionalism, and provides unbiased and useful information.

3.) Social Media Listening/Online Community Engagement

Roles	Expected functions and responsibilities
Project lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Oversees daily operations, trains and supervises staff.
Feedback collection manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supervises daily collection of data including feedback and rumors. ○ Trains partners on data collection and analysis.
Community correspondents/community liaison officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collects data including feedback and rumors, and report these to the project team. ○ Shares useful data and correct information to the community to address rumors and misinformation.
Data Analyst	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manages the database and analyses data collected. ○ Prepares the rumor tracking bulletin and provides overview on the community's feedback, questions, and concerns to the Feedback collection manager and the field staff.
Fact-checker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Researches and conducts information verification to respond to rumors and misinformation. ○ Explains technical or complicated information to the community.

4.) Joint Field Missions/Community Engagement

Roles	Expected functions and responsibilities
Cluster coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensures common service tools on AAP and community engagement are in place and updated.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Facilitates overall coordination with the field level staff and partners. ○ Provides overall technical guidance on scaling-up AAP and conduct of joint community engagement.
Project Managers/Project Coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provides additional technical guidance to the cluster coordinators on the use of the common service tools for assessment, community consultations, and monitoring. ○ Serves as co-lead on any meetings and collaborations.
Field staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Responsible for directly coordinating, liaising, and engaging with the community. ○ Key focal point for organizing any form of community consultations and engagement.

7.) Common Timeline and Categories on Feedback, Complaints, and Other Serious Breaches on Accountability

Each agency has its own way of reviewing feedback and complaints. But for this joint/interagency CFM, it is crucial to have a common understanding of categorizing it, setting the timeline and indicators, and identifying referral process that would facilitate the resolution to any issues or cases.

Using various channels, all agencies and designated staff that will be directly involved in the joint/interagency CFM should be mindful of the key details that would determine the likely response to take and process to prioritize in line with the information received.

The table below is an adoption from previous humanitarian response actions that could be useful to facilitate corresponding actions in the soonest and safest time possible. Agencies working with third party service providers may need to provide additional and contextualized briefing or training on CFM with emphasis on receiving, recording, and referring process.

Codes	Feedback and Complaints Categories	Speed (<i>referring agency</i>)	Timeline (<i>receiving/responding agency</i>)	Resolution (<i>follow up actions on the referral</i>)
0	General feedback (<i>Appreciation, Greetings</i>)	No immediate response required		
1	Request for information	3 -5 days (<i>up to 1 week if referral is needed or required</i>).	3 days upon receiving the referral.	Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency if the referral is: -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered
2	Request for assistance (<i>general, specific, and special</i>)	Immediate or within 24 hours (<i>up to 3 days if referral is needed or required</i>).	3 days upon receiving the referral.	Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency if the referral is: -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered
3	Dissatisfaction with programs or projects' quality and delivery of services	3 to 5 days (<i>up to 1 week if referral is needed or required</i>)	5 days upon receiving the referral.	Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency (immediately) if the referral is: -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered

4	Dissatisfaction with staff's behavior, rude conduct and misdemeanor (abusive language, harassment, and bullying)	3-5 days (up to 1 week if referral is needed and required)	5 days upon receiving the referral.	<p>Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency (immediately) if the referral is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered
5	Abuse of power and other serious breaches on accountability (sexual exploitation and abuse, gender-based violence, fraud, corruption)	Immediate	Immediate	<p>Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency (immediately) if the referral is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered
6	Safety, security, and other life-threatening issues	Immediate	Immediate	<p>Need to indicate or classify by the concerned agency (immediately) if the referral is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Accepted or successfully closed -Further referral needed -Not eligible -No services delivered

8.) On minimum referral process

Aside from speed, accuracy, and quality of addressing and resolving feedback or complaints, the success of any interagency CFM is also dependent on how responsive, safe, and accessible the referral process is and how substantial is the amount of collective effort exerted to resolve issues or cases in the soonest time and resources available.

As one of the processes to close the loop, having a trusted and reliable referral process is crucial to limit and avoid being stuck from moving forward or at loss. Not all feedback or complaints can be addressed immediately by one or two organizations. Feedback or complaints vary as to severity, criticality, and impact. Some may require additional support and even further investigations to ensure proper interventions are served.

Coordination and ensuring that all organizations meet the minimum standards on referral is always hard. Establishing an interagency mechanism to know who to talk to, when, and for what will facilitate both internal and external coordination referrals always pose a challenge. This boils down to the issue, case, topic, or challenge being addressed and the urgency level to respond to it. This process is one of the usual problems encountered by the community members that cause frustrations, conflicts, and huge loss of trust in the system.

All responding agencies are expected to have its own minimum standards for referral, and this must relate to this protocol as part of resolving issues and cases on a shared accountability commitment.

To sustain safe and accountable referral process, all responding agencies must ponder on these critical questions:

- What is/are the main issue(s) that needs to be addressed urgently?
- When and where did this happen? Do we have additional details that may be useful to facilitate and fast track the referral process?
- Where and why should this issue be referred?
- What program or organizations should take this on?
- Who are the contact person, group, and other concerned agencies (with their corresponding information details) that can contacted for the referral?
- How long will the process take to resolve it or if further referral to other agencies are needed?

To facilitate, it is important to establish what key steps that focal points or team from referring agency and receiving/responding agency should do the moment the referral process is activated.

a.) For referring agency:

- Referral focal point/team must be aware of the existing interagency service mapping³⁰ so that services and assistance are accurately identified.
- Referral focal point/team should check if the trusted/preferred CF channels used by concerned individual are functional and responsive.
- Referral focal point/team must always be prepared to assist/facilitate the initial requirements to support concerned individual such as accessing information services available, obtaining the informed consent form³¹, completing the interagency referral form³², and identifying the right or relevant service provider.
- Referral focal point/team should properly record and review the referral made. Its role is not yet done after sending the request to the receiving/responding agency, as referral status needs to be followed up, and lastly, reporting and documenting needs to be completed in compliance with the agreed interagency monitoring platform.
- Referral focal point/team, in close coordination with the responding/responsible focal point/team, needs to analyze and monitor any gaps in the referral process.

³⁰ AAP service directory managed by UNOCHA.

³¹ All agencies must have this, or an interagency form can be adapted as well to 1.) ensure all information and possible options are clear to the concerned individual, 2.) ensure that concerned individual fully understands the choices or decisions made and what other information or service may be needed, and 3.) ensure that the concerned individual understood well that his decisions are voluntary and should not be influenced or forced by others (e.g. family members, friends, community, and even service providers).

³² As part of the referral management, this form is important to capture the minimum information required by the service provider to respond to the referral and determine how quickly the service provider needs to respond to the referral (but take note to assess each case based on its circumstances).

- Referral focal point/team may declare close or successful the referral case once notified by the receiving/responsible agency that response actions or services have been provided.
- Referral focal point/team may declare that the referral process is not successful and may recommend further referral as deem necessary.

b.) For receiving/responsible agency:

- Referral focal point/team should be quick to acknowledge receipt of the referral and confirm acceptance within 24 hours to 48 hours as possible.
- Referral focal point/team assesses and reviews the criteria /eligibility of the issue or case referred. This usually takes time but receiving/responsible agency should be prepared of the likely response, consequence, and additional layers of re-evaluating the appropriate actions
- Referral focal point/team needs to provide feedback in the soonest time possible that the referrals is accepted and a service, response actions, or interventions will be provided or delivered.
- Responding/responsible agency may inform the referring agency that the referral process is closed, successful, complied, or delivered.
- Referral focal point/team also needs to provide the feedback in the soonest time possible that the referral is not accepted and provide explanations or necessary details as may be required.
- Responding/referring agency may refer/forward the case to another relevant service provider³³ and with due diligence, the agency needs to be fully aware of the needed capacities and resources that can be provided within the timeframe.

Maximizing other technical and operational support mechanism

Dealing and addressing serious form of complaints and other serious breaches on accountability require agencies implementing community engagement/accountability activities as well as the AAP Working Group in working directly with the PSEA Network.³⁴ These include reporting or referring of PSEA incidents, supporting technical-level coordination, and maximizing capacities in supporting the oversight of the SEA and other serious breaches in accountability related issues.

For more or additional details of the referral process and arrangement, **please see Annex 1: Interagency Referral Protocol on Complaints, Feedback, and Other Serious Breaches on Accountability.**

³³ Same process will be applied here between the referring agency and the responding/responsible agency.

³⁴ This protocol supports and adheres to the PSEA Network SOP for Community-Based Complaints Mechanism (CBCM) for State of Palestine.

9.) Joint analysis and reporting

This protocol is operationally committed to ensure that feedback and complaints as well as joint/interagency actions to address those are reflected or integrated in the situation reports, humanitarian needs overview (HNO), monitoring/evaluation/after action reviews, and serve as standing agenda within the humanitarian country team (HCT), Inter-Cluster Coordination Group, (ICCG), and other crosscutting thematic networks to sustain accountable leadership.³⁵

To fully maximize this and ensure other agencies can work or collaborate with each other, under the CERF allocation, UNICEF and UNWomen is providing additional technical support through the development or activation of customer relations management (CRM) software/solution for joint/interagency sharing of information, reporting, referral, and resolution of cases or issues.

Both UNICEF and UNWOMEN will work with ONA Solution System Team to co-manage the CRM when it comes to overseeing the case interface and management workflow development, providing capacity building to key staff that will be directly involved in the overall administration, and supporting the technical and operational maintenance.

The CRM software/solution will be an integral component to support the hotline/helpline and other channels dealing with case management and possible integration with the other available platforms such as the social media, humanitarian radio, and others. This is to ensure it has the broader scope for case intakes, facilitates reporting and referral process, and secures the success of resolving issues.³⁶

The CRM will be used, at the minimum, to support interagency process on:

- **Case intake:** recording of cases, complaints, and other issues (*including consent data, case categorization, and assignment*)
- **Case management:** referral and resolution component (*options for responding/receiving agencies and other needed immediate capacities/resources*)
- **Dashboards:** regular updates on monthly or bi-monthly basis using the agreed reporting templates/formats.
- **Administrations/permissions:** this is the process for agencies seeking access to the system and would like to contribute or be part of the joint/interagency reporting.
- **Additional reporting feature:** this pertains to exporting data and customization of reports.
- **Other agencies/third party integrations:** entry point here is the use of hotline/helpline and eventually other channels/platforms.
- **Other CRM functionality:** to be determined as per additional need especially on tracking and monitoring individual cases over time, etc.

The deployment of additional CRM software/solution will adapt or contextualize, as part of its functionality, the common interagency mechanism, data management and responsibility, common timeline and categories on feedback and complaints, minimum referral process, and joint analysis and reporting sections underscored on this minimum operations protocol.

³⁵ Call-To-Action: Interagency Complaints and Feedback Mechanism to Improve AAP at OPT.

³⁶ Theory of Change: Towards achieving more accountable and impactful interagency CFM from **Call-To—Action: Interagency CFM to improve AAP at OPT.**

Managing the CRM will require, at the minimum, the activation of team with corresponding roles and functions that will work closely with the Steering Committee:

Roles	Expected function and responsibilities
CRM Manager/Technical Lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Speak with members of the community to encourage reporting cases and refer the said case to respective focal points for proper reporting. ○ Oversees the case management process, plan resources, and reviews accomplishments and performance trends.
Receiver focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receive and register complaints using the relevant information management tool or booklet used for manual or offline recording.
Referral focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Receives referrals, forwards concern accordingly for proper handling and appropriate actions. ○ Close the loop with members of the community with concerns when the case is resolved
Secondary Referral focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supports the primary focal point in handling reported cases.
Information Management focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Serves as platform administrators in charge of creating and managing user profiles, permissions, and access.

As for the Steering Committee, part of its role is to liaise with responding/receiving agencies supporting the interagency CFM. These include cluster/sector coordinators and focal points, AAP Coordinators and focal points, PSEA Coordinators and focal points, Referral focal points, and Receiving/Responding focal points.

Sharing or publication of reports including trends, dashboards, statuses, and progresses of all cases can be done on a monthly or bi-monthly basis. The Steering Committee can decide to produce additional or separate report that can be shared and eventually used for recalibration of programs or activities with the HCT and ICCG.

10.) Quality Assurance and Minimum Capacity Building

Focal points and concerned staff³⁷ need to have the minimum mandatory capacity building to perform best their respective roles or functions. All responding agencies have the obligations to provide staff and partners with both strategic and technical know-how as part of the onboarding process or as a continuing program to further enhance in-house capacity.

³⁷ Technical, field staff, third party consultants/experts/resource persons, and other implementing/operational partners.

The provision of the capacity building should serve as a supplementary support to ensure that everyone involved in a joint/interagency engagement understood same framework, indicators, timeline, deliverables, expectations, and overall support needed to facilitate the resolution process for issues and concerns.

Experts, specialists, and technical advisors can also provide additional contextualized training that may be necessary to scale-up the ongoing projects/initiatives including:

- Protection against Sexual Exploitation and Abuse (PSEA)³⁸
- Interagency or Agency Specific Code of Conduct Awareness Training
- Accountability to Affected People (AAP)³⁹
- Data Responsibility in Humanitarian Action⁴⁰
- Interagency Service Mapping⁴¹ (including frequently asked questions endorsed/approved by the interagency)
- Protection and Inclusion Mainstreaming⁴²
- Gender in Humanitarian Action (GIHA)⁴³
- Other technical specific training that may be provided by the agency or organized as an interagency initiative (*radio humanitarian programming, customer/case relation management, social media literacy, information management, active listening exercise using various channels, and documentation utilizing analog and digital tools*).

Regardless of the two-way channels and the people that will be engaged, the following skills and techniques are needed to manage and support the joint/interagency CFM:

- **Active listening:** especially on the non-verbal communication/listening or understanding to what is not being said.
- **Interpersonal:** there is no fixed formula how to communicate and engage with people, but dedicated time, right attitude, and proper language are all essential to maximize this.
- **Empathy:** making sense and understanding perceptions and background of people requires more repetitive practice and immersive experience.
- **Coordination:** perhaps one of the overused and misused areas that need to be revitalized every now and then. Any joint/interagency requires a different approach to work with partners and get things done accordingly.
- **Learn, unlearn, and relearn mind set:** knowing how the channels work is one thing, but how to make it accessible, simple, and reliable is another thing.
- **Non-discrimination competence:** understanding core humanitarian principles requires that provision of service and assistance must apply the differentiated gender approach appropriate for the affected people. This includes religion, tribal affiliation/ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender identity, age, disability and distinguishing profile like, level of education, language barriers, solo parent, etc.

³⁸ This could be the IASC module or the agency contextualized PSEA training.

³⁹ AAP has three components: a.) On leadership and governance, b.) programmatic approach, and c.) on CFM and Referral. While CFM will be core for this protocol, it is important for staff to understand that it is only one component that will contribute to the overall accountable humanitarian response actions.

⁴⁰ This could be based on the IASC Technical Brief on Data Responsibility or any existing data management agreement within a particular agency or a joint commitment with other organizations.

⁴¹ If already operational and has the endorsed/approved common service tools available (joint/interagency assessment, community consultations, and monitoring).

⁴² Can be provided by the Protection Cluster and partners upon request.

⁴³ Can be provided by UN Women and partners upon request.

- **Going beyond the obvious:** Receiving feedback/complaints is one thing, but addressing those is another thing. Knowing how the two work will always make a difference.
- **Common sense is all about avoiding intended harm or consequence:** handling sensitive cases requires specialized support services, so make it a habit to always seek support from experts and other agencies as needed and required.
- **Safety/Security Consciousness:** the main priority of operational and field staff is both their and affected people's safety/security in all kinds of two-way dialogue or engagement. All indicators, signs, and alert warnings that would put both sides on further danger must be always avoided.
- **Balanced approach to two-way channels:** it is important to be always mindful of the preferences of the people or community when it comes to communicating or engaging with them. Some may trust those considered analog platforms and may have difficulty adjusting to new or emerging applications.
- **Documentation:** always an underrated skill considering the abundance or advancement of technology and proliferation of artificial intelligence applications. But dealing with feedback/complaints requires good sense of documentation on qualitative data and analysis to inform decision making.
- **Information management:** understanding the purpose of reviewing and recording data can help enhance the use, protection, and storage of received/process information to operate more effectively and improve the CFM system.

11.) Raising Awareness and Reporting Back to the Communities

Pivotal to the success of any joint/interagency CFM is the appreciation and acceptance of the people that it is set up for them, and the overall show of trust or respect by them as on how they are being engaged in the overall management process.

Awareness to the communities on inclusive access to joint/interagency CFM is expected to come from:

- Humanitarian Country Team (*HCT*) and Inter-Cluster Coordination Group (*ICCG*)
- Steering Committee on joint/interagency CFM, other Thematic Working Groups, and partners
- Humanitarian agencies/organizations/groups (*UN, INGOs, Local NGOs, CSOs, Red Cross, and others*)
- Local media
- Community groups/networks
- Volunteers

From the start, people has the right to know:

- How the joint/interagency CFM works (*going beyond the provision of objectives, etc.*)?
- Who are the agencies and concerned people managing or supporting it?
- How inclusive are the channels?

- How responsive is the system of the joint/interagency CFM?
- How they will be informed if there is a corresponding action to their concerns?
- Can they influence the joint/interagency CFM to improve or recalibrate its approach?
- How do they know that all data they shared are safe and taken with utmost confidentiality?

This protocol has provided the details on how to best provide information to the people as part of the overall raising awareness campaign.

But in order to articulate it very well, agencies managing or supporting joint/interagency CFM must:

- Come up with a standard joint/interagency FAQs on the agencies involved, channels used and system established in the overall CFM.
- Explain it to them without the usual humanitarian and technical jargons that would confuse them and complicate the process (*causing distrust and may undermine the humanitarian response actions*).
- Consult people on components that they do not understand when it comes to accessing those channels and trusting the system.
- Monitor how people are responding to the CFM and if there is any improvement on their overall awareness to further support it or not.

To secure people's trust and satisfaction, it is imperative to report back the communities about:

- Status of cases or issues being reviewed or referred.
- The reason or the need to change or make adjustments or recalibrations on the available channels and system supporting it.
- The reason or the need to discontinue or not the joint/interagency CFM.

12.) Sustaining resources and capacities on the joint/interagency CFM

Sustaining the responsiveness and quality to capacities, resources, and other enabling support platform is an investment to the overall accountability and quality of the humanitarian action for OPT like inclusion in the annual budgeting plan and consideration for prolonged displacement.

The following are some of the options to properly and sustainably resourced AAP in humanitarian action:

- **HRP and CERF:** ensure that AAP is prioritized and integrated throughout the humanitarian program cycle (*and beyond if possible*). Agencies such as UNOCHA, UNICEF, UN Women, WFP, and its respective partners have identified various activities under CERF to scale-up meaningful engagement with the affected people.

- **HCT and ICCG support:** as part of oversight and overall accountable leadership, AAP should be a standing agenda in any strategic and technical/operational level decision making to support course correction and recalibration of the humanitarian response programming (*like expanding the implementation of AAP initiatives and commit for additional or more funding support*).
- **Cost sharing:** CERF allocated agencies and other organizations with dedicated budget on AAP related activities should collaborate and continue to identify partnership opportunities to support implementation of joint/interagency CFM. Commitment to allocate funding support should be more than just assigning agency to implement its own specific activities, it should be focus on joint/interagency.
- **Program budget within the agency:** standard budget line for AAP in any country program or project management is necessary as part of scaling it up within the organization and ensuring it can contribute impactfully on improving the joint/interagency CFM.
- **Donor funding:** with support from HCT, continue engaging donors to expand its commitment on accountable humanitarian action.

To scale-up:

- HCT approval/endorsement of the protocol and ICCG's operational support in implementing AAP initiatives with the at-risk communities and affected people.
- Sustaining the AAP-Working Group and PSEA Network collaboration to improve the joint/interagency referral mechanism on SEA related issues and make it more functional or responsive.
- Monitor, evaluate, and recalibrate the usefulness and responsiveness of the identified two-way channels and the system or mechanism supporting it.
- Engage more agencies and organizations as possible to maximize the CRM software/solution supporting the interagency CFM (*sharing of information and reporting*), referral mechanism (*monitoring and closure of cases*), and interagency system (*addressing feedback/complaints and reporting back to the communities*).